

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP6 – Outreach and Sustainability

D6.8 Report on liaison with other BD4BO projects

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Belgium
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL – Switzerland
BI	Boehringer Ingelheim International GmbH – Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

IMI’s Big Data for Better Outcomes (BD4BO) programme was designed to facilitate the use of “big data” to enable the transition towards value-based, outcomes-focused healthcare systems in Europe through the participation of several projects. Within task 6.7, EHDEN has been the entry point for the continuing dialogue between EHDEN and the rest of the BD4BO programme projects.

This deliverable details the joint work done with HARMONY, PIONEER and BIGDATA@HEART.

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1. INTRODUCTION

IMI’s Big Data for Better Outcomes (BD4BO) programme was designed to facilitate the use of “big data” to enable the transition towards value-based, outcomes-focused healthcare systems in Europe through the participation of several projects (Task 6.7). EHDEN enabled initial contacts with HARMONY, PIONEER and BIGDATA@HEART. These initial discussions have evolved into prior signing of Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with each of the projects in order to establish a collaboration framework. Although initially we hoped to organise F2F meetings with the representatives of these projects, the COVID-19 pandemic has imposed the need to continue conversations by virtual means. The mapping of data to the OMOP CDM is a recurring discussion topic across all projects, although not all projects had foreseen the required resources for this activity. Therefore, some BD4BO project partners are planning to apply to our Open Calls for financial support to map their own data to the OMOP CDM and we have seen some evidence of this. In addition, discussions had been initiated to explore organising joint study-a-thons and in particular, planning of a joint study-a-thon between PIONEER and EHDEN which was expedited during 2021.

2. MoU WITH BD4BO PROJECTS

EHDEN initiated the dialogue with BD4BO projects from its start. In order to frame the initial discussions with the projects, we signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with PIONEER, HARMONY and BIGDATA@HEART.

Fig 1. MoU with Harmony

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Fig 2. MoU with BIGDATA@HEART

Fig 3. MoU with PIONEER

3. COLLABORATION WITH HARMONY

EHDEN has had intermittent interaction with HARMONY/HARMONY PLUS, in the main in year three around responding the COVID-19 pandemic, but also around the respective projects' views on sustainability. The EHDEN Project Lead presented at the HARMONY General Assembly in a keynote on lessons learned, challenges and opportunities.

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4. COLLABORATION WITH BIGDATA@HEART

EHDEN has had some minimal interaction with BIGDATA@HEART, principally on our Data Partner calls and OMOP harmonisation process. At the end of year three there were further discussions on the potential study-a-thon being considered by BIGDATA@HEART for 2022, and the EHDEN Project Lead presented at their General Assembly on this subject.

5. COLLABORATION WITH PIONEER

5.1 Initial discussions

There have been more in-depth discussions between EHDEN and PIONEER in two key areas, potential collaborative use cases for evidence generation and methodological development in Health Technology Assessment, and also on Outcome Standards (ICHOM) driven by EHDEN WP2 and PIONEER WP6, and secondly on a collaborative study-a-thon held in March 2021, led by PIONEER with EHDEN and OHDSI colleagues.

5.2 Collaboration on HTA and Outcomes

This interaction has focused on agreement on the best use case, approach and resourcing between the projects, with more current success around HTA. EHDEN hopes to be able to initiate a collaborative HTA use case with PIONEER in our year four. Initial discussion between the projects has identified the area of “treatment sequencing in prostate cancer” as a mutually beneficial use case. EHDEN WP2, and principally colleagues from NICE are driving this work with colleagues from PFIZER and JANSSEN in terms of proposed methodological use cases. We aim to establish an agreement for cross-work package collaboration in early 2022 and to report on further progress on the use case in RP4.

5.3 Joint study-a-thon

In March 2021 a [study-a-thon](#) was held by PIONEER with EHDEN and OHDSI colleagues, with more than 240 researchers internationally. The research focus was to use OMOP-mapped real world datasets (17 internationally) to evaluate real world outcomes for prostate cancer patients managed with guideline directed ‘watchful waiting’ versus active treatment or active surveillance. As PIONEER is also directly linked to the European Association of Urology and guideline evaluation is a critical requirement too. EHDEN was involved hands on with OHDSI colleagues in the inception, execution and follow up of the study-a-thon, based on our experience, expertise relevant colleagues. We will continue the collaboration for future joint study-a-thons, especially not only due to the evidence generation, but also their educational value.

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A blog post about the EHDEN contributions to PIONEER was published in the EHDEN website: [The PIONEER study-a-thon: how EHDEN collaborates with its sister projects to generate medical evidence \(https://www.ehden.eu/the-pioneer-study-a-thon/\)](https://www.ehden.eu/the-pioneer-study-a-thon/)

6. NEXT STEPS

EHDEN looks forward to working with our sister BD4BO projects in year four, particularly on initiatives that may focus on evidence generation, education and sustainability. This will follow the steps identified in the prior comments to our RP3 report above (sections 3,4 and 5).

A clear emphasis in BD4BO is outcomes, and this is a critical output in terms of outcome research for all of our projects.